

MODELING WING LEADING EDGE MADE WITH SLM LATTICE CORE AND CFRP SKIN

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1 General Introduction

Selective laser melting (SLM) is an additive manufacturing technology that uses a high-powered Ytterbium fibre laser to fuse fine metallic powders together to form functional 3-dimensional parts – lattice structures. Fig. 1 shows two typical lattice cubes.

Fig. 1. 20 mm cube lattice structures based on a) the BCC unit cell and b) the BCC-Z unit cell [1].

Research into the lattice structures has shown excellent energy absorbing characteristics, high quality, repeatability and a controlled collapse mechanism. It has been shown that by carefully designing the architecture of the unit cells within the lattice, the energy absorbing characteristics can be tailored to meet the needs of a variety of different applications. The SLM process can be ‘scaled up’ to produce larger, more complex structures can easily be created with a view for use in the aerospace industry. The structures combination of high performance and lightweight shows a potential use in the manufacture of aerospace components, such as nose cones, leading edges and cockpit shields.

A range of wing leading edge lattice structures was manufactured using the SLM process. Carbon fibre composite skins were cured to the outer surface of the lattice to create a sandwich panel. Fig. 2 shows such the structure. Such components must be designed to withstand impact loads from a variety of sources such as hail, bird strike or runway debris.

Fig. 2. The WLE structure [1].

This paper presents numerical modeling of structural behavior of wing leading edge (WLE) made with SLM lattice core and CFRP skin. Here, the lattice core was modeled as a crushable foam material with strain hardening, whilst CFRP as an orthotropic linear elastic material up to failure followed by damage initiation and evolution using Hashin criteria. Impact response of WLE subjected to a drop hammer projectile load was simulated. Simulations were compared with the experimental results, in terms of load-displacement relationships, deformation and failure modes. Reasonably good correlation was obtained.

2 Finite element modeling

2.1 SLM lattice core

The lattice core in the sandwich WLE structure was modeled as crushable foam using hardening curves obtained following compression tests on square lattice samples. It was assumed that the Poisson’s ratio of all of the foams was 0.32. Deshpande and Fleck [2] proposed a phenomenological yield surface for a closed-cell foam material, given by:

$$\varphi \equiv \frac{1}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right)^2\right]} \left[\bar{\sigma}^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_m^2 \right] - \sigma_y^2 \leq 0 \quad (1)$$

where σ_y is the uniaxial yield strength (in tension or compression) of the foam, $\bar{\sigma}$ is the Von Mises stress, and σ_m is the mean stress. The term α describes the shape of the yield surface, which is related to the ratios of the initial uniaxial yield stress, σ_c^o , and the hydrostatic tensile yield stress, p_t , to the hydrostatic compressive yield stress, p_c^o , respectively. The yield stress in hydrostatic compression, p_c describes the development of the size of the yield surface and is given as:

$$p_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) = \frac{\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left[\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^2} + \frac{1}{9} \right) + \frac{p_t}{3} \right]}{p_t + \frac{\sigma_c(\varepsilon_{pl}^{vol})}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where ε_{pl}^{vol} is defined as the plastic volumetric strain in the volumetric hardening model, and is set equal to ε_{pl}^{axial} the compressive plastic strain. The term, p_c can therefore be determined from a compression test on the foam.

Here, it is assumed that the response of a rate-dependent solid obeys the uniaxial flow rate definition, which is given as:

$$\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl} = h(q, \bar{\varepsilon}_{pl}, \theta) \quad (3)$$

in which the term h is a strain-hardening function, $\bar{\varepsilon}_{pl}$ is defined as the equivalent plastic strain, and the parameter θ is the temperature. The rate-dependent hardening curves can therefore be expressed as:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}(\bar{\varepsilon}_{pl}, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}) = \sigma_y(\bar{\varepsilon}_{pl}) R(\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}) \quad (4)$$

in which $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}$ and R are defined as the equivalent plastic strain-rate and the stress ratio ($= \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_y$) respectively.

Ductile damage was included in the crushable foam material model to remove elements that were excessively warped. The ductile fracture model assumes that the equivalent plastic strain at the onset

of damage, $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}^D$, is a function of the stress triaxiality and the strain rate: $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}^D(\eta, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl})$, where $\eta = -p / \bar{\sigma}$ is the stress triaxiality, p is the pressure stress, q is the von Mises equivalent stress and $\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}$ is the equivalent strain rate. Ductile fracture will initiate when the following condition is satisfied:

$$w^D = \int \frac{d\bar{\varepsilon}_{pl}}{\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}^D(\eta, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl})} = 1 \quad (5)$$

where, w^D is a state variable that increases monotonically with plastic deformation. At each increment during the analysis, the incremental increase Δw^D is computed as:

$$\Delta w^D = \int \frac{\Delta \bar{\varepsilon}_{pl}}{\dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl}^D(\eta, \dot{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{pl})} \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

In this study, it was assumed that the fracture strain was 0.65 and the stress triaxiality was 1.4 for all strain rates. Damage evolution of the elements was based on the energy dissipated during the damage process. The fracture energy per unit area, G_f , was set to 240 J/m².

2.2 CFRP skin

Prior to damage initiation, the CFRP skin was modeled as an orthotropic elastic material. The elastic modulus values of the plain weave skin were assumed to be equal in the longitudinal and transverse directions. Damage initiation was modelled using Hashin's failure criteria [3] which assumes four damage initiation mechanisms, namely fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression.

The initiation criteria have the following general forms:

Fibre tension:

$$F_f^t = \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{11}}{X_T} \right)^2 + \alpha_s \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

Fibre compression:

$$F_f^c = \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{11}}{X_C} \right)^2, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} \leq 0 \quad (8)$$

Matrix tension:

$$F_m^t = \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

Matrix compression:

$$F_m^c = \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{2S_T} \right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_T} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{12}}{S_L} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

where X_T, X_C are tensile and compressive strengths in the longitudinal direction, Y_T, Y_C are tensile and compressive strengths in the transverse direction, S_L, S_T are longitudinal and transverse shear strengths, and α_s is a coefficient that specifies the contribution of the shear stress to the fibre tensile initiation criterion. $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}, \tilde{\sigma}_{22}, \tilde{\sigma}_{12}$ are components of the effective stress tensor, $\bar{\sigma}$. The material properties used to define damage initiation for the CFRP material are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Damage initiation data for the CFRP.

X^T (MPa)	X^C (MPa)	Y^T (MPa)	Y^C (MPa)	S^L (MPa)	S^T (MPa)
850	500	850	500	90	90

Using the longitudinal, transverse and shear effective stress tensor components within the plane of the CFRP, the damage initiation criteria can be determined.

The damage elastic matrix, which relates the stress and strain and controls degradation of the material stiffness, can be expressed as:

$$C_D = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)/E_1 & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{21}/E_1 & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{12}/E_2 & (1-d_m)/E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-d_s)GD \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where G is the shear modulus and D is an overall damage variable, dependent upon the current state of fibre (d_f), matrix (d_m) and shear (d_s) damage, respectively.

2.3 Mesh generation and boundary/loading conditions

Fig. 3 shows the mesh generation of the half WLE sandwich structure and the WLE-NC (i.e. without lattice core) structure. Here the face sheets are meshed by 8-noded continuum shell elements with reduced integration, whilst the lattice core by 8-noded solid elements with reduced integration. The CFRP skin was modelled with two plies, each with a thickness of 0.25mm. There are various interfaces in the model to be dealt. The bottom edges of the CFRP and the lattice core were fully fixed as in the experimental tests and a tie constraint was used to fix the CFRP skin to the lattice core.

Fig. 3. Mesh generation.

In modelling the quasi-static indentation tests, a displacement boundary condition was applied to a reference point, placed at the bottom of the rigid indenter. This moved the indenter downwards at a

steady rate, perforating the structure. The reference point was used to record the displacement and reaction force from the WLE structure.

In the drop-weight indentation tests, a point mass equal to one half of the mass of the experimental drop-weight carriage was applied to the reference point on the rigid indenter. An initial velocity was prescribed to the indenter, equal to the impact velocity employed in the drop-weight experiments. The displacement and acceleration of the reference point was recorded in the drop weight models. The load was calculated by multiplying by the recorded acceleration of the indenter by its mass.

A general contact algorithm was used to define contact between the surfaces of the indenter, the CFRP skin and the lattice core. The interaction properties were set to 'hard' in the normal direction, and a friction coefficient of 0.4 was defined in the tangential direction. The general contact algorithm allows for the use of element-based surfaces to model surface erosion during analyses. It considers a face only if it's underlying element has not failed and is not coincident with a face from an adjacent element that has not failed. Thus, all exterior faces in a model are initially active while interior faces are initially inactive. The faces of an element will be removed from the contact domain when the element fails and any interior faces that have been exposed after the removal of the failed element will be activated. A contact edge is removed when all of the elements that contain the edge have failed. Based on this algorithm, the active contact domain evolves during the analysis as elements fail.

An element surface was created for the lattice core and was included in the general contact interaction so that the elements below the surface of the structure would contact the indenter as the structure is damaged. For computational efficiency, only the elements in the vicinity of the indenter we included in the element surface.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Quasi-static indentation

The load versus indentation depth plots for the WLE and WLE-NC structures are shown in Figure 4. The load behaviour of the WLE structures displays a

non-linear response up to the point of initial failure of the CFRP skin at a depth of approximately 3mm. Prior to the failure of the CFRP skin, deformation occurs as a result of a combination of bending of the CFRP and elastic-plastic deformation in the lattice core. The residual strength of the CFRP skin maintains the level of load between the initial failure to a displacement of approximately 12mm, where complete failure of the CFRP skin occurs. After this point, the lattice core supports the load as the indentation continues. The experimental traces show excellent repeatability of the mechanical properties of the structure.

Fig. 4. Plots of load vs. indentation depth, comparing experimental and FE model data for a) WLE structure and b) WLE-NC structure.

The load behaviour of the WLE-NC structure also displays a non-linear response up to failure of the CFRP skin. The structure shows a reduced stiffness compared to the WLE structures with lattice cores. Failure of the CFRP skin occurs at an indenter depth of approximately 10mm, where an abrupt drop in the

load is observed. After this point, the bending of the fractured edges of the CFRP skin support the reduced load up to a displacement of 14mm where complete failure of the skin occurs. The WLE-NC structures show excellent repeatability in the initial stiffness but the structures exhibit variation in the fracture load.

A summary of the test results and the corresponding numerical simulations on the WLE and WLE-NC structures are presented in Table 2. The FE models show a similar response to the experimental tests, where the initial stiffness, initial failure load and post-failure response are accurately captured. As the WLE and WLE-NC structures had different masses, the specific properties were calculated for each structure and are given in Table 2. The table shows that the specific initial stiffness of the structures is approximately equal, whereas the WLE-NC structures have approximately double the specific energy absorption capability than the WLE structures.

The response of the WLE structure and corresponding FE model, at increasing indentation depths, is shown in Figure 5. The images show that the overall deformation of the structure is minimal and suggests that the damage to the structure is localised to the region of contact between the structure and the hemispherical indenter. The images also show that the FE model accurately captures the

response of the WLE structure.

The response of the WLE-NC structure and corresponding FE model, at increasing indentation depths, is shown in Figure 6. The images show that the WLE-NC structure deforms in a global manner. Initially, bending of the CFRP skin occurs in the sides of the structure and deformation occurs at the point of contact. This continues up to the point of failure in the CFRP at approximately 10mm. After this point, the deformation at the point of contact increases as the CFRP material tears, whereas the deflection of the side walls of the skin reduces after failure. The images show that the response of the WLE-NC structure is accurately predicted in the FE model.

Figure 7 shows the area of contact between the indenter and the WLE and WLE-NC structure. The images show that the damage is localised for the WLE structure and that the CFRP skin is permanently deformed. The WLE-NC structures regain their initial shape but show cracks in the material in the directions of the fibres.

3.2 Dynamic response

Drop-weight impact tests were conducted on the WLE and WLE-NC structures. An instrumented carriage with a 10mm hemispherical indenter was dropped from heights of up to 0.7m. Corresponding FE models were created and compared to the experimental results.

Table 2. Summary of the results from the quasi-static indentation tests and FE predictions.

Specimen ID	Mass (g)	Initial stiffness, k (N/mm)	Indentation depth (mm)	Energy absorbed (J)	Energy absorbed up to fracture (J)	Specific energy absorbed (J/kg)	Specific initial stiffness (kN.kg/mm)	Peak load (N)
WLE-B2-1	37.0	400.6	19.8	8.1	6.4	217.9	10.83	663.4
WLE-B3-7	38.3	418.1	20.3	7.5	5.9	195.2	10.92	578.4
WLE-B3-8	35.2	473.7	30.0	9.7	5.8	275.2	13.46	546.3
WLE FE	36.8	383.3	20.0	7.9	6.2	214.8	10.41	647.6
WLE-NC-B3-1	7.2	74.3	16.5	2.9	2.2	406.3	10.32	448.4
WLE-NC-B3-2	7.5	68.0	16.0	3.4	2.4	449.9	9.07	505.2
WLE-NC-B2-1	7.2	70.2	14.8	2.7	1.6	368.4	9.75	380.1
WLE-NC FE	7.3	71.5	15.0	3.95	3.14	541.5	9.80	556.2

The dynamic response of the WLE structure was similar to the quasi-static response. Plots of load versus indentation depth for the WLE structure, at various impact velocities, are presented in Figure 8. The plots follow the same trend as observed in the quasi-static tests. An increase in the peak load of approximately 8% was observed in the dynamic tests compared to the quasi-static values. This response is mirrored in the corresponding FE models where an increase in the peak load of approximately 9% was found.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the collapse of the WLE structures in the experiments and the FE models

The FE models accurately predict the overall response of the WLE structures with the indentation

depth, peak load and energy absorbed being predicted to within approximately 15% of the experimental values.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the collapse of the WLE structures with no core in the experiments and the FE models.

The dynamic response of the WLE-NC structure was also similar to the quasi-static response. The load versus indentation depth plots for these structures are shown in Figure 9. The plot shows an increased stiffness compared to the quasi-static test data and a drop of approximately 9% in the average peak load, though the indentation depths at fracture were similar. The plots show better repeatability than observed in the quasi-static results. The FE model of the WLE-NC structure accurately predicts the initial

stiffness of the structure but over-estimates the peak load and displacement at failure of the CFRP.

Fig. 7. Images of the contact areas of a) the WLE structures and b) the WLE-NC structures.

Fig. 8. Plots of load vs. indentation depth for the WLE structures at impact velocities of a) 2.58 m/s, b) 3.36 m/s and c) 3.95 m/s comparing experimental and FE model data.

Fig. 9. Plots of load vs. indentation depth for the WLE-NC structures at an impact velocity of 2.67 m/s comparing experimental and FE model data.

A summary of the test results and the corresponding numerical simulations on the WLE and WLE-NC structures subjected to projectile impact are presented in Table 3. The FE models show a similar response to the experimental tests, where the initial stiffness, initial failure load and post-failure response are accurately captured. As the WLE and WLE-NC structures had different masses, the specific properties were calculated for each structure and are given in Table 3. The table shows that the specific initial stiffness of the structures is approximately equal, whereas the WLE-NC structures have approximately double the specific energy absorption capability than the WLE structures.

Table 3. Summary of the results from the drop-weight impact tests and the corresponding FE modelling.

Specimen ID	Impact velocity (m/s)	Impact energy (J)	Indentation depth (mm)	Peak Load (N)	Absorbed Energy (J)	% Impact Energy Absorbed
WLE-B3-4	2.50	4.7	9.6	647.0	3.86	82.15
WLE-B4-6	2.64	5.2	9.0	635.7	4.34	82.74
WLE-B3-3	2.62	5.2	11.7	514.6	4.62	88.99
WLE-1 FE	2.58	5.0	11.1	699.8	5.0	100
WLE-B3-6	3.40	8.7	22.4	587.9	7.51	85.92
WLE-B3-1	3.31	8.3	17.3	700.7	7.09	85.50
WLE-2 FE	3.36	8.5	22.7	709.7	8.5	100
WLE-B2-2	3.97	11.9	33.2	622.6	10.21	85.73
WLE-B4-2	3.99	12.0	29.6	671.8	10.35	86.12
WLE-B3-5	3.90	11.5	26.1	751.3	10.63	92.69
WLE-3 FE	3.95	11.8	36.7	724.4	11.6	98.1
WLE-NC-B5-1	2.59	5.1	40.0	355.5	2.33	46.01
WLE-NC-B5-2	2.76	5.7	40.0	456.3	2.85	49.60
WLE-NC-B5-3	2.67	5.4	40.0	410.1	2.68	49.72
WLE-NC FE	2.67	5.4	40.0	595.6	5.0	93.6

4. Conclusions

Finite element models have been developed to simulate wing-leading-edge structures with and without SLM lattice cores. The FE models developed are capable of accurately predicting the response of the WLE structure under quasi-static and dynamic loading. Further analysis of the CFRP material is needed to improve the characterisation of the material properties.

The WLE and WLE-NC exhibited different collapse mechanisms during the indentation tests. Deformation in the WLE structure was localised, whereas the WLE-NC structures deformed globally. The WLE structure showed permanent deformation of the CFRP skin, making damage identification easier than the WLE-NC structures, where the structure regained its original shape but with cracks in the CFRP in the direction of the fibres. All those features were captured in the FE modeling.

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